

Session title: E4. Imaging, Biomarkers, Diagnostics

Session type: Posters: Theme E : Vascular Diseases

Presentation number: 624

★ **Abstract title:**
EARLY COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT AFTER MINOR ISCHEMIC STROKE

V. Milosevic¹, J. Basic², M. Zivkovic¹.

¹Clinical Center Nis, Clinic of Neurology, Nis, Serbia.

²University of Nis, Faculty of Medicine, Nis, Serbia.

Abstract body

Cognitive impairment is registered in more than 80% of ischemic stroke patients. Early cognitive impairment, registered immediately after stroke is characterized by partial recovery within a few months.

The aim of this study was to assess early cognitive impairment after minor stroke (NIHSS \leq 5).

We have included 35 patients with ischemic stroke and 30 age matched controls. The clinical diagnosis of stroke was determined by a patient history of symptoms, a neurological examination, and neuroimaging techniques (CT and/or MRI). Patients were assessed 10 days, 3 months and 12 months after stroke. Neurological impairment was measured using the National Institute of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS). Cognitive function was assessed by the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA).

The age difference and the level of education between stroke patients and the healthy controls was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The average NIHSS was 5.20 ± 3.20 on admission, 2.70 ± 0.91 at the time of the first assessment, 2.21 ± 0.81 and 2.11 ± 0.79 at a time of the follow-up assessments. MoCA scores in stroke patients during the first two assessments were significantly lower than in the healthy controls (MoCA - 10 days 21.30 ± 4.42 vs. 25.34 ± 2.11 ; $p < 0.05$ MoCA - 3 months 22.34 ± 6.11 vs. 25.34 ± 2.11 ; $p < 0.05$). However, MoCA score differences were not statistically significant one year after stroke onset.

Cognitive impairment can be measured in patients with minor stroke up to three months after the stroke onset.

Keywords:

stroke

Cognitive impairment

Friday, March 29th, Exhibition

Session code: E4

Session title: E4. Imaging, Biomarkers, Diagnostics

Session type: Posters: Theme E : Vascular Diseases

622: ASSOCIATION OF PLASMA LIPIDS WITH VASCULAR DEMENTIA

 [N. Braidy](#)¹, Y. Liu¹, A. Poljak¹, D. Chan², P. Sachdev¹.

¹Centre for Healthy Brain Ageing- School of Psychiatry, Faculty of Medicine- University of New South Wales, Randwick, Australia.

²Bankstown-Lidcombe Hospital, Department Aged Care and Rehabilitation, Bankstown, Australia.

623: APHASIA AS PROGNOSTIC FACTOR FOR COGNITIVE AND FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN PATIENTS WITH STROKE

 [J. Hyun](#)¹, S. Kim².

¹Dankook University, Rehabilitation Medicine, Cheonan, Republic of Korea.

²Dankook University Hospital, Rehabilitation Medicine, Cheonan, Republic of Korea.

624: EARLY COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT AFTER MINOR ISCHEMIC STROKE

 [V. Milosevic](#)¹, J. Basic², M. Zivkovic¹.

¹Clinical Center Nis, Clinic of Neurology, Nis, Serbia.

²University of Nis, Faculty of Medicine, Nis, Serbia.